

OPTIDECK – THE SMART FRP PANEL FOR BRIDGE REDECKING – DEVELOPMENT AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Maciej Kulpa, Rzeszow University of Technology, Poland, kulpa@prz.edu.pl
Mateusz Rajchel, Rzeszow University of Technology, Poland, mrajchel@prz.edu.pl
Bartosz Piątek, Rzeszow University of Technology, Poland, piatek@prz.edu.pl
Tomasz Siwowski, Rzeszow University of Technology, Poland, siwowski@prz.edu.pl

ABSTRACT

The objective of the presented research is the development of a FRP composite bridge deck panel. The honeycomb sandwich structure were determined using FEM simulations. An advantage of the panel is a structural health monitoring system based on distributed fiber optic sensors installed inside the laminates. Both the new deck structure and the SHM system were verified in laboratory tests ranging from small material coupons to full-size panels. The latter included static, fatigue as well as dynamic excitation tests. The tests confirmed the appropriate stiffness, load carrying capacity and feasibility of strain and displacement measurements with Distributed Fibre Optic Sensors (DFOS) monitoring system.

KEYWORDS

Optic fibre, SHM, Bridge Decks, Sandwich

INTRODUCTION

Ageing infrastructure is becoming more and more significant problem for many developed countries. Due to the increasing traffic volume of heavy vehicles and aggressiveness of the environment, in combination with the need for maintenance with salt in winter, RC bridge decks are much less durable than other bridge elements. Increasing awareness of the importance of structural durability and resistance to aggressive external environment caused that the new material solutions are being sought, investigated and applied in civil engineering applications, especially including bridge engineering. One of the answers to this situation is the use of FRP composites for the production of bridge elements (Qureshi, 2023).

Composite structural bridge components are relatively young solution, but thanks to their lightweight, high strength, resistance to environmental condition and corrosion as well as high durability, their development and improvement is currently the subject of numerous research projects. All FRP composite bridges have been in service on public roads worldwide for over 20 years. The majority of these all-composite bridges is performing well, although there have been a few cases where they have created problems for the bridge owner and were taken out of the service. FRP sandwich structures are highly susceptible to damage due to delamination, matrix cracking, interlaminar fracture and debonding, all of which have potential to cause catastrophic structural failure. Therefore, as with any structural elements used for bridge structures, it is necessary to be able to inspect FRP structural elements, even if most of them are hidden under asphalt layers.

For many years, examining and verifying the proposed theoretical solutions was based on the laboratory experiments under carefully controlled conditions. It is, of course, an essential step in the whole process of introducing the new solution to the market. However, the measurements carried out under real operating conditions are more and more appreciated recently. Laboratory researches are not able to reflect long-term structural operation, including changeable external conditions or cooperation of the structure with the substrate characterized by the random and changeable parameters. So, it is not possible to clearly answer the question if theoretical predictions will be correct in real operation conditions over long term. That is why SHM systems are becoming increasingly appreciated in civil engineering applications, particularly in safety-critical facilities such as bridges (López-Higuera, et al., 2011).

One of their main goals is to provide objective and useful information about the actual structural condition. Thanks to the early warning provided by SHM systems, remedial actions can be taken immediately providing both the increasing in safety and financial savings. Designing structures able to self-diagnosis and early damage detection is one of the challenges for design engineers related to the 4.0 revolution and the Internet of Things. Distributed fibre optic sensing (DFOS) is a very promising technology in the context of assessment of technical condition, local damage detection and recording the overloaded vehicles (Barrias et al, 2016).

NEW PANEL IDEA

Structural concept

Composite decks are most often produced in one of two technological processes: pultrusion or infusion. In the case of composite elements, the choice of the production process determines the shape and form of the target element. For pultrusion, because of a production limitations, these are most often panels consisting of interconnected profiles. The choice of infusion means that we can create whole element in one process. On the other hand this process is more difficult to automate. However, relatively small financial outlays at the initial stage of production mean that sandwich panels made in the cheaper infusion method are the most commonly used structural system of composite deck panels in road bridges (Siwowski, 2018) and was adopted as structure for new developed bridge deck, called "OptiDeck".

This sandwich panel usually consist of light core inserted between two laminates. The new deck panels are designed with lower and upper multilayered glass-epoxy laminates and the polyurethane (PUR) foam core. In the case of the "OptiDeck" panel, the core was additionally reinforced with internal vertical laminates. The experience from the tests of previous types of FRP decks made it clear that the most appropriate solution would be ribbing the core in the form of a structure imitating a honeycomb (Kulpa & Siwowski, 2018; Kulpa et al., 2020). This assumption resulted in the fact that between the vertical laminates there were foam in the form of prisms with a hexagonal base (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Idea of construction and production of a deck panel with full foam core and honeycomb ribbing

An overview of the existing solutions and own preliminary calculations showed that the weakest point of sandwich panels is the connection of vertical laminates of ribs with horizontal laminates (Davalos et al., 2013). It was decided to solve this problem by an individual and innovative production process. It consisting in wrapping prefabricated foam hexagonal prisms with dry fabrics, and then laying them in the form of a plate. The ribs of the core are formed during the infusion of the resin, and thanks to the method of wrapping of the cores, the fabrics from the vertical ribs became part of the outer laminates. As a result, not only resin, but continuous fibers participated in this connection and determined the load carrying capacity of this connection (Kulpa et al., 2022).

The foam core prisms were prefabricated from polyurethane foam slabs. The foam of density 30 kg/m³ and at least 86% closed cell content were used. A two-component matrices produced by Hunstmann was used to infusion of the glass fibers in the deck panels. It consists of Araldite epoxy resin with Aradur amine curing agent. It was necessary to developed this individually combination of ingredients to obtain low exotherm and viscosity needed to receive the correct saturation of all fabrics,

especially vertical fabrics tightly placed between foam prisms. After preliminary calculation and simulation, the dimensions of individual foam prisms were determined to be 240 mm height and 180 mm diagonal of the base. A semi-automatic method of VARTM (Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding) was selected for the production of composite decks (Kulpa et al.,2022).

Figure 2: Structural diagram of a sandwich panel with the location of fiber optic sensors

SHM system

Local damage detection is now one of the main functionalities, that structural health monitoring systems should be equipped with. However, this goal is almost unachievable for conventional, spot measurement techniques, even if they are supported by advanced mathematical and numerical simulations. Sensors located in several points of the structure allow us to observe general trends in structural behaviour, what is of course important thing, but they are not able to directly indicate the place, size and the reason of local damage occurrence. What is more, special caution must be kept during data interpretation, as the measured strain (stress) values in a given structural point strongly depend on sensor's location.

The new quality for structural monitoring and assessment of technical condition through in situ measurements, provide distributed fibre optic sensing (DFOS) technology (Culshaw & Kersey, 2008, Kulpa et al., 2021a). This technique allows to effectively replace thousands of traditional spot gauges with a single optical fibre sensor.

a) A cross-section of a standard optical fibre in its primary acrylate coating b) An idea visualisation of a double sensor grid within one external laminate

Figure 3: Elements of the DFOS monitoring system

DEVELOPMENT

Material testing

All laboratory tests were carried out at the Rzeszow University of Technology. Material tests have been planned to achieve two goals (Kulpa et al., 2021b):

- obtaining a set of material constants used to describe the material (such as stiffness modules and Poisson's coefficients) and strength parameters (compressive, tensile, shear strength, etc.);
- a test of installing the sensor inside the composite material before production and carrying out measurements with their use.

The presentation of the fulfillment of both of these objectives will be presented on a tensile tests. These specimens were rectangular with the width of 25 mm, the thickness of 2 mm and total length of 300 mm (measuring section between the tabs was 150 mm). The most important sensor in the sample was the optical fibre embedded in the centre of the cross section (no. 3 on fig. 4a) along the entire specimen's length. Parallel with the sensors placed inside the laminates, additional optical fibers (measurement routes) were placed on the outer surfaces of the samples both in the axis of the sample and near its edges (Fig. 4a). Thanks to this, it was possible not only to compare the reliability of both types of sensor locations (inside and outside the laminate), but also to comprehensively assess the behavior of the sample under load, taking into account possible bending moments caused by non-axial mounting in the testing machine and unavoidable imperfections in the execution of samples. Sensors glued to the outer surfaces of the samples were attached in two ways: along the entire length with epoxy glue (marked D) and at points at the ends of the measuring section with cyano-acrylic glue (marked P). In this way, a quasi-string sensor was created.

Figure 4: Tensile material tests

When only one side was measured by DFOS, the second was equipped with the reference typical electrical strain gauge (esg). The force increase during the test was 10 kN/min. Due to the application of the optical reflectometer for static measurements, the tensile process was carried out in steps of 5 kN. After reaching the required load value, the testing machine was stopped for the DFOS measurements.

Fig. 5a shows the strain distributions measured by the internal fibre in subsequent load-steps. The measurements by this sensor were carried out until the failure of the sample. The maximum measured strain was 2.8% (28000 $\mu\epsilon$). The effect of the tabs crimping was observed, causing that strain values are the highest in the middle of the specimen and the lowest in the area near to the tabs. The strain values in the middle of the sample measured at successive load levels are shown in Fig. 5b. Based on the results, the sample behaved linearly throughout the entire load range, with no signs of non-linear behaviour.

a) Strains measured on length of an internal optical fibre b) Strains increments in the middle of the internal fibre

Figure 5: Example results from a sensor placed inside a material sample

The measurements using surface optical fibres were possibly only in the range of strains not exceeding the 1%. Continuously-bonded fibre has produced the similar results as in the case of internal fibre, where the shape of strain profile could be analysed in detail, while spot-attached fibre (marked P) averaged strains along the entire measuring length (Fig. 6a). Hence, the straight lines presented in Fig. 6a represent the mean strain values for sample. The reasons why surface fibres were not able to measure strain correctly in the full range are as follows:

- breakage of the fibre's primary coating initiated by a notch at the edge of the cyanoacrylate adhesive (for point-attached fibre, marked P);
- partial debonding of the two-component epoxy, preventing the appropriate strain transfer from the composite specimen to the glass measuring fibre (for continuously-bonded fibre, marked D).

As the tests showed, the sensors glued to the outer surfaces were most often damaged before the destruction of the sample itself. The force causing the detachment of the sensors was variable and was in the range of approx. 50-90% of the force destroying the sample itself. An example comparison of the readings obtained from the internal, external optical fibers and the reference electroresistance strain gauge (esg) is shown in Fig. 6b. Differences in the slopes of the curves are due to inevitable notches and geometric imperfections, but each sensor recorded an elastic, linear response of the sample to the applied load.

a) DFOS glued along the length (D) and at two points (P) b) DFOS internal, external and esg sensors

Figure 6: Comparison of results obtained from variously installed DFOS sensors and measurements with esg sensors

For example, in case of B02 sample the last reliable data from surface-mounted fibres were obtained for the force value of 15 kN, while internal optical fibre worked correctly up to the force of 35 kN (Fig. 6b). DFOS measurements were also compared with the reference foil strain gauge, which withstood the force of 20 kN, corresponding to the strain of approx. 1.4%. The last measurement was obtained during the force of 25 kN (real strain of 1,8%) but it was just before the gauge's breakage

and this record does not reflect the real behaviour of the specimen. It is clearly visible that the fiber optic sensor placed inside the sample allowed measurements up to the moment of sample's destruction, and therefore can be considered as the most reliable of all the compared measurement techniques.

The material tests allowed for a preliminary assessment of the effectiveness of the proposed measuring method through optical fibres integrated inside the composites. Material tests confirmed that this approach does not require surface installation (elimination of adhesive's debonding and cracking phenomena) and thus allows the strain to be measured in the full range until the specimen destruction. What is more, integration of the fibre inside the composite means that the sensor is naturally protected against mechanical damages. It should be emphasized that the internal optical fibre was arranged along entire length of the specimen i.e. also through the area of tabs, which were compressed with a great force by the jaws of the testing machine.

FEM

For the numerical analysis of the Optideck panels, a model consisted of two-dimensional finite elements in three-dimensional space was made in the ABAQUS program. All laminates (face sheets and internal ribs) were modeled using four-node shell elements with unreduced integration of the S4 type. Material coordinates 1, 2, 3 were determined based on the actual orientation of the fibers in the individual fabrics (0, 90 or ± 45). The foam filling the spaces was not modeled in the numerical model (treated as a non-structural element).

All elements of the numerical models were discretized individually with a maximum mesh size of approx. 20×20 mm (Fig. 7). The general meshing technique was designed so that all nodes created in the contact areas were convergent. In order to generate the mesh, the appropriate shape of the finite elements and the meshing method were selected depending on the geometry of the part.

Figure 7: Numerical models in the abaqus environment

The numerical models represented the actual support of the panel, taking into account the stiffness of girders for operating stage (Kulpa et al., 2022) and a laboratory load scheme as supported on steel roller bearings. The laboratory boundary condition was reproduced by removing the degrees of freedom from nodes located in the place of translational supports, implementing the scheme of a simply supported beam. Nodes lying in the axes of support were prevented from translational displacement in the gravitational direction. On the axis of one of the extreme supports, translational degrees of freedom in the direction of the panel axis were also blocked, thus implementing a non-sliding bearing (Fig. 8).

Depending on the purpose of the model, different load schemes were used. A laboratory load scheme with a contact area of 0.4×0.4 m was implemented. The load was set both in the middle of the width of the panel and on the edge in the middle of the span (Fig. 8b, 8c). The maximum load was applied to the full capabilities of the laboratory loading system, up to 1260 kN for total load. This load was applied to the upper surface of the plate elements (top laminate) of the panel and was modeled as pressure.

Figure 8: Various boundary conditions and load schemes in numerical models

EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

Due to the prototype nature of the new deck panel, many experimental cases of the key elements were carried out. The main purpose of these tests was to confirm the correctness of the assumptions adopted at the stage of designing and to experimentally confirm the load carrying capacity and its stiffness. Experimental tests also made it possible to assess the fatigue load capacity and dynamic characteristics in terms of meeting the requirements for road bridge decks in this respect.

Experimental tests made it possible to obtain sets of data (i.e. values of displacements, deformations) and failure forms, which were used for verification and validation of methods of analysis (both analytical or numerical). The whole scope of experimental program of the deck system included:

- static and dynamic tests of the panel at designed 2,4 m simple supported span;
- several static and fatigue tests of the beam elements of the deck slab panel, created by cutting a full panel to smaller samples.
- dozens of samples of connection between deck panels and conventional main girders (concrete or steel) or between adjacent panels.

The variety of laboratory samples was so significant that it is not possible to present here all results of the conducted research. Therefore, in the following, the presentation is limited to the results obtained from the static tests of the full-scale panel.

The tested deck panel has a total length of 2.615 m, a span of 2.40 m and a width of 1.25 m. In static test, the panel was loaded in a three-point bending scheme using two hydraulic jacks with a maximum force of 630 kN each (Fig. 9). The load was applied in two variants, i.e. in the middle of the panel width (symmetrical load) and close to the edge (asymmetric load) (Fig. 8). The contact area of each steel load-distributing element and the panel panel was 0.40×0.40 m. A layer of mortar was placed between the panel's upper side and steel plate beneath the traverse beam, which ensured an even distribution of the load on the panel.

Fig. 9. Test stand of the platform panel in the three-point bending scheme

The static load on the panel was carried out in several stages with a pair of forces increasing from 0 to 1260 kN (2×630 kN). Load values in individual stages are shown in Fig. 10. The load application speed was 15 kN/min. The force was measured with a dynamometer and reported in real time.

Figure 10: Stages of loading the panel

During the static tests, displacements and deformations of the panel model were measured at characteristic points and cross-sections. In addition to DFOS system, a total of 37 conventional measuring points were used to evaluate the behavior of the panel under static load. 17 inductive sensors were used to measure the displacements of the panel. Deformations of the panel were measured using 27 foil strain gauges with a measuring base of 10 mm. All measurement data was collected using the HBM Spider acquisition system with a set of QuantumX amplifiers. All results were recorded with a frequency of 2 Hz.

The structure was inspected for possible damages when maximum load was applied and when panel was unloaded. There wasn't global failure during the tests and also no local damage was observed in any of the loading stages. The final confirmation of the correct panel's operation and its construction was the comparison of the panel displacement results measured during the tests with the results based on numerical simulations. The results of the experiment were highly consistent with the results of displacements (Table 1), and the several percent underestimation was probably due to the conservative omission of foam as a non-structural element in the models.

Table 1: Consistency between displacements during laboratory tests and numerical simulation in 19 measuring points

Load arrangement	Load [kN]	Consistency [%] (experiment / simulation)		
		Min.	Max.	Average (from 19 points)
symmetrical	1000	80,3	91,4	91,4
asymmetrical	630 + 0	79,2	91,0	86,6
asymmetrical	630 + 630	79,1	92,4	87,7

To verify the accuracy and functionality of the DFOS system, the optical measurements were compared with those obtained from conventional measurements using electric strain gauges. In Figure 11, the measured strain distribution along one of the sensor (C4) is presented with corresponding spot values read using electric strain gauges arranged in selected locations along the optical sensor's axis. To check the compliance under the entire load range, several load cycles were chosen for data presentation. The most variable data (along the whole panel's length) from the top side of the upper face laminate was selected for comparison. The comparative visualisation in Figure 11 is complemented by the accurate measuring data summarised in Table 2.

The very good compliance of results from DFOS and common electric strain gauges results was obtained. Usually, relative differences were from a few to several percent, while the mean difference is only about few percent (Table 2). It shows very good accuracy of DFOS strain measurement as compared to the reference technique. The small differences are mainly due to the different locations

of the DFOS fibres (inside the laminate) and foil gauges (on the laminate's outer surface) as well as the possible minor discrepancies in determining the exact positions of strain gauges in relation to a specific point of optical fibres.

Figure 11. Comparison between DFOS strain distribution (sensor C4) and results of common strain measurement technique (esg) for the upper face laminate.

Table 2: Comparison between DFOS strain distribution and results of common strain measurement technique (esg) for the upper face laminate (load of $2 \times 250 = 500$ kN)

Location from support [m]	Strains [$\mu\epsilon$]		Δ (DFOS – esg) [$\mu\epsilon$]	Δ / esg [%]
	DFOS	esg		
0.28	-661	-637	-24	3.6
0.54	-907	-952	45	-5.0
0.81	-1249	-1269	20	-1.6
1.35	-1234	-1304	70	-5.7
1.63	-1051	-961	-90	8.6
Mean difference:			42	-4.9

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this ongoing research was the development of a FRP composite bridge deck panel with the intention of applying to redecking the deteriorated bridge decks. The appropriate honeycomb sandwich structure of the FRP deck panel were determined using FEM simulations.

Both the new deck structure and the SHM system were extensively verified in laboratory tests ranging from small material coupons to full-size panels. The conducted laboratory tests confirmed the very high load capacity and stiffness of the sandwich panels. The tested full-size sandwich panel did not fail globally under the maximum achievable test load of 1260 kN applied in the middle of the panel span. Therefore the global load capacity of the panel bending moment is higher than 756 kNm, which translates to 630 kNm/m (for the tested panel with a width of 1.20 m). The panel at the full load range behaved linearly and elastically. Permanent deformations and displacements were below 2% of the maximum values. It should be emphasized that no differences were observed in the global load capacity in the direction of the longitudinal and transverse axes of the panel, which proves that the sandwich panel is almost quasi orthotropic. The test results were very satisfactory from the design point of view.

The system of optical fibres for distributed strain and displacements measurements was integrated with the multilayered laminates during their production (infusion) process, enabling to create smart structural components as one prefabricated elements. The appropriate integration of optical fibres within the composite laminates was verified during the production of the full-scale prototype deck panel and its laboratory tests, which confirmed the technical feasibility of strain and displacement measurements with DFOS monitoring system. Strain and displacement results from DFOS system during three-point bending were compared to alternative measuring techniques and finite element analysis (FEA). The comparison showed the fine agreement of the results and emphasized the

advantages of geometrically continuous measurements, which allow the observation of local phenomena, such as bending of external facesheet over inner webs. The smart FRP deck panel, integrated with DFOS system for SHM and dedicated for bridge redecking, turned out to be very promising in the context of the performance and durability of bridges.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.